

INVESTIGATION OF N-(2-AMINOETHYL)-2-PHENOXYACETIC ACID AMIDE AS A BIOSIDE IN BAKU BASE OILS**Farzaliyev V.,***Dr. of Chemical Sciences,
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In order to prevent the rapid development of microorganisms (bacteria and fungi) that have a negative effect on the quality of lubricating oils, the synthesis of organic compounds containing various functional groups and their research as biocides are relevant.

In the article, an organic compound synthesized at the Institute of Additives Chemistry - amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid - has been extensively studied as a biocidal additive in Baku base oils. Taking into account that this compound is soluble in oil, its biocide property was studied in M-8 Eastern oil, and also comparative physico-chemical parameters were studied in the composition of samples in new lubricant compositions of biocide taken at a concentration of 0.25-0.5% of M-14ГБ motor oil used in marine diesels.

Based on the results obtained, it was established that the addition of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid amide as biocide to the composition of oil samples does not adversely affect the indicators of important physico-chemical and operational properties of the lubricant composition of M-14ГБ motor oil, while protecting them from the negative effects of bacteria and fungi.

Keywords: synthesis, base oil, biocide, lubricant composition, additive, operational properties, biological sustainability.

In the operation of modern machines and mechanisms, when they are stored for a long time, when they are transported, as well as when they are exposed to biological damage, their protection by means of various biocides is one of the urgent problems [1].

It should be noted that oil and oil products are sensitive to microbiological effects. When they are stored for a long time, when they are transported, as well as during operation, they are exposed to the negative influence of microorganisms and suffer microbiological

damage. The main microorganisms that cause biological damage to lubricating oils are: bacteria of the genera *Pseudomonas*, *Nicrococcus*, *Mycobacterium* and also *Cladosporium*, *Aspergillus*, *Repicillum*, *Alternaria*, *Aeruginosa* and *Cladosporium* fungi.

In order to prevent the rapid development of microorganisms (bacteria and fungi) that have a negative effect on the quality of lubricating oils, various chemical substances are being synthesized, and organic compounds containing new functional groups are being studied as biocides. Research conducted in the field of

studying the biocidal properties of synthesized organic compounds confirms the possibility of creating effective additive compositions against biodamage [2,3].

In the article, extensive studies amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid synthesized at the Institute of Additive Chemistry as a biocide were carried out in Baku and Eastern base oils.

where $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_2\text{COOH}$ - phenoxyacetic acid;
 $\text{H}_2\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{H}_2$ – ethylenediamine.

The 3-necked flask equipped with a Dino-Stark stirrer, thermometer, dropping funnel and reflux condenser. 7.6 g (0.05 mol) of phenoxyacetic acid, 0.6 g of catalyst p-toluene sulfonic acid, 120 ml of toluene are heated in the flask, then 3 g (0.05 mol) of ethylenediamine is added little by little. The reaction is carried out at a temperature of 109-110 °C for 5 hours until complete water separation. As a result, 0.9 ml of water is separated. After the water is removed, the residue has a crystalline appearance. As a continuation of the process, flammable crystals are again boiled in solvent - benzene, filtered through filter paper and allowed to crystallize. The crystals are light brown. The yield of the substance is 8 g (82.5 %). Melting point 110 °C, gross formula $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$.

The presence of functional groups in the synthesized compound allows us to make a certain opinion about the fact that this compound has different functional properties as an additive. In this regard, in order to study the research areas of the obtained compounds, their functional properties (effect against microbes, corrosion, corrosion) in oil and lubricant coolants were studied.

The anti-biodegradability effect of synthesized compounds has been tested in M-8 oil, synthetic oil and lubricating-cooling fluids. Tests were carried out on ГОСТ 9.052-88, ГОСТ 9.082-77, ГОСТ 9.085-78 in M-8 and synthetic oil (1-0.25%), for lubricating and cooling liquids (0.5-0.25%), respectively. The tests were carried out using pure cultures of microorganisms

The amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid was synthesized from the interaction of phenoxyacetic acid with ethylenediamine in a toluene medium at a temperature of 109-110°C in the presence of a p-toluenesulfonic acid catalyst.

The chemical reaction and methodology of the synthesis are given below:

widely distributed in petroleum products and aggressively damaging them.

Meat extract B agar was chosen for bacteria, and malt extract agar was chosen for fungi.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa, *Mycobacterium lacticolium*, and *Mycobacterium phlei*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria were found in oil.

Aspergillus niger, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Penicillium cyclopium* were taken in oil for fungi, and *Aspergillus niger*, *Chaetomium globosum*, *Cladosporium gossipicola*, *Cladosporium resinal* were taken for lubricant-cooling liquid

Planting of microorganisms is carried out on the surface of the nutrient medium. To determine the zone of destruction of microorganisms, 4-5 holes with a diameter of 10 mm and a depth of 4-5 mm are opened on the medium surface with a sterilized stick. Oil without biocide and with biocide and a percentage solution of lubricating coolant is added to these holes. Petri bowls are kept in thermostat at a temperature of $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours for bacteria in lubricating-cooling liquids, 5-7 days for fungi, 2-3 days for bacteria in oils, 5-7 days for fungi. The effectiveness of the antimicrobial property of the studied compound is determined by the size of the diameter (in cm) of the zone of destruction of microorganisms (with or without additives). The larger the zone, the higher the antimicrobial property of the additive.

The biocide efficacy of the synthesized compound was tested in lubricating-cooling liquids, M-8, M-14ГБ and synthetic oil, and its results were given. The amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid has fungicidal properties in all 3 indicators. Table 1.

Table 1.

Investigation of antimicrobial properties the Amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid as a biocide in different oils

Combinations		Microorganisms destruction zone diameter, sm		
		Biocide concentration,%	Bacteria (Meat extract B Agar)	Fungi (malt extract agar)
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ + lubricating-cooling liquids		0.5	++	1, 6-1,7
		0.25	++	1, 4-1,5
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ + Synthetic oil		1.0	++	1, 4-1,5
		0.5	++	1, 2-1,3
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ + M-8 East oil		1.0	++	1, 3-1,4
		0.5	++	1, 1-1,2
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ + M-14ГБ		1.0	++	1.2-1.3
		0.5	++	1.1-1.2
Control	Lubricating-cooling liquids	With out biocide	++	++
	M-8 East oil		++	++
	Synthetic oil		++	++
	M-14ГБ motor oil		++	++

* $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ - N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid amide, biocide

As can be seen from Table 1, the best result - as a result of the inclusion of biocide in fuel lubricants (lubricating-cooling liquids) at a concentration of 0.5% (the diameter of the zone of destruction of fungi is 1.6-1.7 cm, and the addition of 0.25% - 1, 4-1.5 cm) is obtained. However, increasing the concentration of biocide in synthetic oil and M-8 oil (when adding 1.0%) makes the diameter of the fungal destruction zone 1.4-1.5 cm. These results are considered satisfactory and confirm that phenoxyacetic acid ethylenediamine urea has fungicidal properties.

Taking into account that the synthesized substance is soluble in both oils, its effect as a biocide in M-8 East oil was studied and the main physico-chemical and operational indicators were determined. (Table 2.) As it can be seen, the main quality indicators of the sample of M-8 East oil with biocide were not changed. Thus, it was determined that adding it to the oil at a concentration of (0.25-0.5%) does not have a negative effect on the main physico-chemical parameters of the oil.

Table 2.

Amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid on M-8 East base oil comparative study

Indicators	Examples		Test method
	M-8 East oil	M-8 East oil + 0.25% Biocide *	
Kinematic viscosity, mm ² /s 40 °C 100 °C	60,62 7.67	60,61 7.64	GOST 33 ASTM D445
Viscosity index	88	89	GOST 25371 ASTM D2270
Ignition temperature set in open put, °C	238	239	ASTM D92
Freezing temperature, °C	Minus 36	Minus 36	GOST 20502 Method A, according to option 2
Dynamic viscosity, mPa/s, °C Minus 15 °C Minus 20 °C	6804 23431	6804 23431	ASTM D 5293
Corrosivity, in lead plates, g/m ²	212.0	210.0	GOST 11362 ASTM D 7394
Persistence based on sedimentation induction period, 30 hours	0.5	0.5	GOST 20284 ASTM D 1500
Tribological properties: Scraping index, S _i Crisis load, P _b Welding load, P _q Eating diameter D _y	310N 88N 784N 1.00mm	457N 588N 980N 0.46mm	GOST 9490 ASTM D 2266

* Biocide - amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid

A new lubricant composition of M-14ГБ oil was created by adding OLOA-9999 of the foreign multifunctional additive package to the M-10 base oil obtained from the compound of M-8 East oil and M-13.0 Baku base oil: Viscoplex-2-670 – viscosity additive (Germany, "Evonik"), OLOA-9999 - multifunctional additive package (USA, "Oronite"), Lubrizol-6446 - detergent-dispersant additive (USA, "Lubrizol"), Vis-

coplex-5-309 - low freezing temperature release depressant additive, ПМС-200А (Russia) – polymethylsiloxane, antifoaming additive [4].

The created lubricant composition fully meets the requirements of GOST 12337-84 for M-14ГБ oil. By adding biocide in the amount of 0,25% to this lubricant composition, an effective lubricant composition against biodamage was prepared and their physico-chemical and operational indicators were studied. (Table 3.)

Table 3.

Amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid comparative study of M-14 ГБ lubricant composition

The name of indicators	Base oil M-10 (M-8 East+M-13,0 Baku (45:55))		Test method
	Biocide free	With 0.25% Biocide *	
	0,8%V *-2-670 2,0%OLOA-9999 0,25%Lz-6446 0.5% V *-5-309 0.003% ПМС-200А	0,8%V *-2-670 2,0%OLOA-9999 0.25% Lz-6446 0.5% V *-5-309 0.003%ПМС-200А	
Kinematic viscosity, mm ² /s 40 °C 100 °C	139,7 14,36	138,8 14,32	GOST 33 ASTM D 445
Viscosity index	101	101	GOST 25371 ASTMD 2270
Corrosion, on GOST 3778 in lead plates of C1 or C2, g/m ²	There is no	There is no	GOST 20502 Method A, according to option 2
Alkali number, mgKOH/1g oil	6.0	6.4	GOST 11362 ASTMD 7394
Sulfate ash, %, ,	0.784	0.752	GOST 12417 ASTM D 95
Color, in the colorimeter ЦНТ	4.0	5.0	GOST 20284 ASTMD 1500

* Biocide - amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid

* V- Viscoplex polymethacrylate additives

It was determined that the inclusion of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid amide as a biocide in the lubricant composition did not cause any changes in the physico-chemical and operational properties of the oil, and all the physico-chemical and operational indicators of the lubricant composition remained at the same level.

Based on the conducted research, we have developed a new bio-resistant lubricant composition of the well-known M-14ГБ engine oil against biodamage.

M-14ГБ motor oil is widely used in marine diesels. In 2017, scientists of the institute received an Azerbaijani patent for this oil. [5] This the effectiveness of motor oil is explained by the additives used in its composition: detergent-dispersant, multifunctional additive against oxidation and corrosion - AKI-130 (carbonated calcium salt of the condensation product of alkylphenol with formaldehyde and ammonia); dispersing-neutralizing additive C-250 (colloidal dispersion of calcium carbonate and hydroxide stabilized with calcium sulfonate in И-20А oil); anti-oxidation, corrosion and corrosion additive -A-22 (dialkyldithiophosphate solution in mineral oil); polymethacrylate viscosity ad-

ditive - Viscoplex-2-670; polymethacrylate-type additive, depressant - Viscoplex-5-309; antifoam additive, polymethylsiloxane – ПМС-200А (sample I) .

M-14ГБ engine oil is used in marine diesels in a complex operating mode and is more sensitive to biological damage, which made the creation of its bio-sustainable lubricant composition urgent. Therefore, a new bio-sustainable lubricant composition was created by adding the newly synthesized substance as a biocide in the amount of 0.25% (sample 2).

Sample I. Base oil M-10 (Baku); add-on package: 3.7% AKI-130; 1.4% C-250; 0.9% A-22; 0.8% Viscoplex 2-670; 0.4% Viscoplex 5-309; 0.003% ПМС-200А.

Sample II. Base oil M-10 (Baku); add-on package: 3.7% AKI-130; 1.4% C-250; 0.9% A-22; 0.8% Viscoplex 2-670; 0.25% Biocide *, 0.4% Viscoplex 5-309; 0.003% ПМС-200А.

* Biocide - amide of N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-phenoxyacetic acid

Table 4.

Comparative study of M-14ГБ commercial motor oil, known oil and new bio-sustainable lubricant composition

Indicators	M-14ГБ motor oil	Examples	
		Example 1	Example 2
Kinematic viscosity , mm ² /s, 100 °C	13.5±14.5	13.9	14.0
Viscosity index	90	92	91
Alkaline number , mgKOH/1g oil	5.9-6.6	8.0	8.0
Sulfate ash , %	1.6-1.75	0.81	0.80
Mass quantity of mechanical mixture, %	0.01	0.008	0.01
Ignition temperature in open put Appointment, °C	220	237	23 6
Freezing temperature, °C	Minus 10	Minus 15	Minus 15
Corrosiveness, in lead plates, g /m ²	There is no	There is no	There is no
Washing property by ПЗВ method, point	-	0	0
Durability based on the induction cycle of precipitate formation, 50 hours	Continue brings	Continue brings	Continue brings
Color in ЦНТ colorimeter , ЦНТ unit (diluted (15:85)	It is not normalized	4.0	4, 0
Laundry potential , 250 °C, %	-	85	85

As can be seen from the table, the addition of biocide to the M-14ГБ lubricant composition not only ensures its anti-biodegradability effect, but also does not adversely affect the quality indicators of this oil.

References

1. Evdokimov A.Yu., Fuks I.G. Oblashchikova I.R. Environmental aspects of chemical lubricants M.: Oil and gas, 2001, c.197.
2. Ermolenko Z.M., Shtuchnaya G.V., Martovetskaya I.A. // Physiological, ultrastructural and

morpho-population features of *Mycobacterium flavescens* bacteria, which utilize oil and petroleum products / Biotechnology, 1996, No. 5, p. 17-24.

3. Melnikov V.N. Technology of biocidal processing of lubricating oils // Сб. scientist _ tr. / ЦИГАУ. 2001.

4. Additives company Rohmax Evonik Industries, 2008, www.rohmax.com

5. Patent of Azerbaijan I 20170015.